

GENERATION OF ELECTRET STATE IN COMPOSITE POLYMERIC MATERIALS BY FRICTION

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SUMMARY: During operation of metalopolymeric frictional systems, a triboelectret state is generated in dielectric polymer materials due to intensive electrophysical processes. As it follows from the analysis of the energy balance at friction, a part of mechanical energy is used to generate a triboelectret state in polymers during the run-in stage, and maintains the same at steady operation. The following topics are discussed: generation of electret state, effect of electret state on friction and wear, electret-triboloelectrification superposition in the course of polymer friction. Electret state resulted from the fabrication pre-history of the materials, processing technology, etc. Mechanical activation of powder is accompanied by increasing its structural imperfection, density of surface states, and, as a result, by higher parameters of electret state. The experimentation conducted allowed to establish that presence of a filler in electret state in a composite affects polymer electrification in the course of frictional interaction with metal. Depending on the vector's direction of field intensity created by electret filler's particles, the field generated by triboelectrification can be either weakened or strengthened, i.e. the principle of electret-triboelectrification superposition is realized. The parameters of frictional interaction can be controlled.

KEYWORDS: friction, wear, electret, electrostatic interaction, electrization, triboelectrification, superposition, bearings.

INTRODUCTION

Intense electrophysical processes in dielectric materials employed in metal-polymer friction pairs generate their triboelectret state. It is strongly governed by the electrostatic interactions between contacting surfaces and the magnitude of the adhesion component of the force of friction.

GENERATION OF TRIBOELECTRETS AND THEIR EFFECT ON FRICTION AND WEAR

The analysis of the energy balance in friction indicates that a portion of the mechanical energy goes to generate the triboelectret state in a polymer during the run-in and to maintain it in the stationary conditions of friction. Indications of the appearance of the charge $1-10 \mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$ in specimens subjected to friction; persistence of the charge up to 160 days and the presence of a

spectrum of thermally stimulated currents (TSC) have allowed to identify the electret state of polymers during friction in fluids, such as dielectrics and electrolytes [1,3]. It has been noted that friction in fluids with various electric conductivity increases the general effect of adsorption processes upon the magnitude of the generated charge more than the electric resistance of the medium. The appearing electret state (ES), in its turn, affects the chemophysical processes in friction of polymers. In particular, the adsorption processes evolve primarily on the surface electrically active centers of solids, therefore, the appearing electret state makes polymers more reactive in tribochemical processes [2].

Appearance of the ES in traditional polymer electrets may be attributed to the accumulation of charges due to the injection and polarization caused by orientation of dipoles. It has required to study the electret effect in nonpolar (HDPE) and polar (PVC) polymers. In order to monitor the effect of temperature upon the ES kinetics the friction test would be discontinued after a certain fixed temperature is reached in the friction zone.

The analysis of TSC-graphs of HDPE coatings (Fig. 1) proves that two trapping levels exist with a corresponding low temperature peak within the range $T = 348\text{--}358\text{ K}$ and a high temperature peak within the range $T = 388\text{--}403\text{ K}$. The depth of traps (the activation energy) has been estimated for the first level using the 'initial rise' technique [3] which turned out to be within the range $1.07\text{--}1.8\text{ eV}$ ($10.33\text{--}173.7\text{ kJ/mol}$) in response to the temperature T in the friction zone. Trapping centers in polyethylene are known to appear when the activation energy is within the estimated range causing structural modifications.

Fig. 1: TSC diagrams of HDPE coatings after friction against steel counterbody ($p = 0.2\text{ MPa}$, $v = 1.0\text{ m/s}$) at temperature in friction zone: 1, 323 K; 2, 333; 3, 353; 4, 373 K.

Thus, considering that polyethylene is nonpolar, the TSC magnitudes are positive and the position of the peaks on the temperature scale correspond to the relaxation transitions and estimated activation energy levels, so it can be asserted that generation of ES in PE is due to the injection processes. The observed TSC spectra in polyethylene are caused by the charge liberation when separate links, segments and larger kinetic units are displaced [4].

Unlike the nonpolar partially crystalline PE, a negative polarity peak within the glass transition temperature range T_g in the TSC spectrum of the amorphous polar PVC (Fig. 2)

proves that in this case the ES is generated by the injection of charge carriers from the metallic counterbody assisted by dipole polarization. The negative peak ($T=343\text{--}348\text{ K}$) within the glass transition range (T_g of PVC is 345 K) is due to the molecular mobility, the amorphous phase and the dipole segment α -process. The positive peak observed above T_g , i.e. at $358\text{--}363\text{ K}$, is caused by the relaxation of space charges injected during friction due to the ohmic conductivity. Each relaxation process has its typical duration which depends upon the temperature according to the known Eqn. 1 of Boltzmann-Arenius:

$$\tau_i = B_i \exp(V_i / kT) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 2: TSC diagrams of PVC coatings after friction ($p = 0.2\text{ MPa}$, $v = 1.0\text{ m/s}$) at temperature in friction zone: 1, 303 ; 2, 313; 3, 323; 4, 333; 5, 343 K..

The relationship between the effective volume of the kinetic unit W_k and factor B is expressed by the Eqn. 2:

$$W_k = [B^6 (6kT/\rho)^3]^{1/5} \quad (2)$$

Based on the TSC-diagrams the parameters of relaxation (according to Fig. 2) for the negative peak have been determined using Eqns. (1) and (2). Table 1 shows the results. Their analysis indicates that the estimated parameters correspond to the λ -process of relaxation. The relaxation time according to [5] is $\tau_i = 10^2 \text{--} 10^4\text{ s}$ at $T = 300\text{ K}$, the activation time is $V_i = 30\text{--}50\text{ kJ/mol}$, the kinetic unit volume is $W_k = 10^{-23} \text{--} 10^{-24}\text{ M}^3$. Also, according to the negative peak position corresponding to the glass transition temperature on the scale (Fig. 2, curve 4), absence of the negative peak in the experiments, once they were suspended before this temperature is reached, (Fig. 2, curves 1–3), proves that the α -process of relaxation takes place in this case. Apparently, the observed abnormality is caused by the specific friction effects when both macro- and microvolumes of contacting bodies get involved with their sizes after friction transfer reaching $10^{-19} \text{--} 10^{-20}\text{ m}^3$. It is accompanied by the orientation and

elongation of molecular chains in the direction of friction. Hence, the negative peak on the TSC-graphs of PVC specimens is due to the α -process of relaxation in friction with greater parameters usually because of dispersion and orientation by friction.

Table 1: Parameters of relaxation in PVC coatings subjected to friction.

Temperature in contact zone T_c , K	Activation energy U_i , kJ/mol	Relaxation time τ at $T=300$ k, s	Dimensional factor V , s	Kinetic unit volume W_k , m^3
333	69.9	13217	$7.2 \cdot 10^{-9}$	$4.1 \cdot 10^{-23}$
343	59.8	9013	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$4.3 \cdot 10^{-22}$
353	63.7	8715	$7 \cdot 10^{-8}$	$6.4 \cdot 10^{-23}$
* Activation energy is determined by the 'initial rise technique'.				

Thus, the electret state in PVC coatings in a direct couple of friction on the steel counterbody appears in the following way: when members come into contact and go apart the charge carries are injected into the polymer and localize over the trapping centers or surface states. As the temperature of the contacting bodies increases the molecules are liberated and dipole groups get oriented in the direction of friction and in the injected charge field. The friction process is known to be accompanied by the orientation of segments of the molecules of the polar groups in the main and transferred material in the direction of the force of friction which may cause polarization. It is caused by the mechanical (the effect of the normal and tangential forces) and electrostatic (the inner field effect produced by electrization) factors. The degree of this effect upon polarization depends upon the structures and physical behavior of contacting materials [3]. The TSC-graphs (Fig. 2) allow to conclude that the parameters of the negative (dipole) peak governed by the numbers of oriented dipole groups, are determined primarily by the space charge magnitude injected into polymer by friction. It means that the orientation of dipole groups in PVC is produced by the internal field created by injected charge carriers (the electrostatic factor) and the orientation produced by friction.

It has been earlier demonstrated that current inversion, as a general regularity of polymers triboelectrification, proves the intricacy of these processes and their adequate relationships with the chemophysical processes in polymer surface layers. The TSC-graphs for PVC coatings during various stages of the electrification (Fig. 3) indicate that the moments of time before and after inversion coincide with the earlier established temperature effects in the friction zone upon the ES generation in friction (Fig. 2, curves 1,2 and 4,5), because the temperature in the contact zone (Fig. 3, curve 1) $T_h=306$ K corresponds to that in experiments 1 and 2 (Fig. 2, curves 1,2); $T_h=346$ K (Fig. 3, curve 3) correspond to the temperature in experiment 5 (Fig. 2, curve 5).

Table 2: ESCD (σ , $\mu\text{C}/\text{m}^2$) of HDPE coatings triboelectrified at various friction velocities in couple with dielectric counterbody (relative humidity 65–75%).

v, m/s	Counterbody material					
	PCA		HDPE		PTFE	
	n_{1-}/n_{1+}	σ_{1-}/σ_{1+}	n_{2-}/n_{2+}	σ_{2-}/σ_{2+}	n_{3-}/n_{3+}	σ_{3-}/σ_{3+}
0.3	100/0	57/-	36/64	6/11	71.29	20/5
0.5	100/0	47/-	22/78	10/17	67/33	28/11
0.8	100/0	60/-	71/29	11/5	50/50	28/13
1.1	100/0	46/-	86/14	14/2	80/20	31/19
1.4	100/0	58/-	100/0	8/-	0/100	-/9

Note. All PCA specimens were positively charged.

Fig. 3: TSC diagrams of PVC coatings for different stages of triboelectrification process: 1, prior to electrification current inversion; 2, moment of inversion; 3, after inversion.

A typical feature of the TSC spectrum at the moment of inversion is a significant reduction (5–10 times) of the intensity of the positive peak at 353–363 K. The notion ‘the moment of inversion’ is conventional, only the moment of approaching to such inversion can be implied in experiments. Proceeding from the temperature in the contact zone, then $T_k=328$ K (Fig. 3, curve 2) is an intermediate temperature for experiments 3 and 4 (Fig. 2), when T_k magnitudes are equal to 323 and 333 K, respectively, the pattern of TSC-graph 2 (Fig. 3) can be considered intermediate between graphs 3 and 4 (Fig. 2). Yet, a significant reduction of the positive peak intensity at 353–363 K proves that both the surface layers (e.g., desorption) and the bulk of the polymer experience strong transformations [10]. Hence, the tribological behavior closely relates to the appearance and relaxation of ES in a polymer.

The positive peak at 343 K (Fig. 2, 3, curves 1,2) should be noted separately. The analysis indicates that it occurs in the case when the friction zone is much less heated than the glass transition temperature. Apparently this peak is due to depolarization under the effect of the

field of injected charges when the thermally stimulated discharge appears, it has nothing to do with structural modifications of the polymer during electrification and electretization.

Triboelectretization in the contact between two dielectrics (polymer-polymer) deserves interest. High density polyethylene (HDPE) was tested in the form of coatings 350–400 μm made of the polyethylene powder melt by pressing it at 5 MPa during 0.3 ks at 473 K to aluminum foil substrates. The dielectric counterbody was made from polycapromide (PCA), HDPE and polytetrafluorethylene (PTFE). The original roughness of rollers 0.7–0.45 μm was prepared with abrasive paper. The tests were configured as a shaft on a partial insert at a nominal pressure 0.1 MPa, the friction torque, the temperature of the specimen and current parameters were registered synchronously. The wear rate of coatings and rollers were evaluated by weighing after continuous operation during 1.8 ks. The air relative humidity varied within 65–75%. The effective surface charge density (ESCD) characterizing the degree of triboelectrification was measured using the compensation technique with the help of a vibrating electrode. The thermally stimulated depolarization current (TSC) of the coatings was registered using aluminum electrodes at a linear heating rate 2.5 deg/min. The results were averaged relative to the air humidity variations.

The results have allowed to establish (Table 2) that the magnitude and the polarity of the residual, hence the generated tribocharge on the coatings strongly depend upon the dielectric behavior of the counterbody material and the friction mode. The HDPE coatings in contact with the polar PCA at the friction velocities used become negatively charged. The same coatings in contact with the nonpolar PTFE and HDPE acquire an unstable residual tribocharge: the specimens may become both positively and negatively charged under the same friction conditions. Table 2 demonstrates that the growing friction velocities change the ratio between the negatively and positively charged specimens and between the mean ESCD magnitudes. The dominating charge polarity changes from positive to negative when the counterbody is HDPE and vice versa when it is PTFE. The ESCD inverts at friction velocities 0.5–0.8 and 1.1–1.4 m/s, respectively. The mean ESCD magnitudes change most extremely in contact with PCA, HDPE and PTFE as the friction velocities grow (passing through the maximum) satisfying the relationships $\sigma_{1-} > \sigma_{3-} > \sigma_{2-}$; $\sigma_{2+} \approx \sigma_{3+}$.

The above friction couples differ by the friction coefficients, the temperature of specimens and the wear rates (Table 3). The above parameters are typically the minimum for HDPE – PCA systems and the maximum for HDPE – PTFE systems. Tables 2 and 3 show that higher wear rates and higher friction velocities accelerate the charge inversion.

Table 3: Tribological characteristics of the HDPE – dielectric friction pairs ($p = 0.1$ MPa, $v = 0.8$ m/s, $t = 1.8$ ks).

Counterbody material	T, K	Friction coefficient	Wear rate I_g , kg/(m ² m)	
			HDPE coating	polymer roller-counterbody
PCA	305	0.15	$1.72 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$1.65 \cdot 10^{-7}$
HDPE	333	0.21	$6.92 \cdot 10^{-7}$	$4.20 \cdot 10^{-6}$
PTFE	346	0.24	$5.50 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$3.72 \cdot 10^{-5}$

Since these polymers have different work functions, different surface (water adsorption) and frictional behavior, it can be assumed that the charge inversion is due to the change of the dominating charging mechanism when the friction velocity is altered.

It has been demonstrated above that the polymer electrets are a classic example of disordered systems. Also, the effects play a substantial role in the polymer electrets. friction of polymers can be assumed as an integral process accompanied by a wide variety of electrophysical phenomena. Apparently, they interact with a possible feedback, self-control and self-restoration [11,12].

Possibilities of the appearance of an autoregulating system in the process of evolution and relaxation of the electret states of polymers in friction is a worthwhile study. Therefore, the cascading (intermittent) friction mode was used for experimentation with the electrophysical parameters. The experiment was configured as follows: HDPE films 300–320 μm produced by hot pressing were subjected to the cyclic friction at $p = 0.1$ MPa and $v = 1$ m/s during variable time periods t in the cascading mode with the interval τ between cycles. Common techniques were applied to check the parameters of the electret states of coatings after friction by measuring the effective surface charge density (ESCD) and thermally stimulated currents (TSC). Initially the effect of friction duration upon triboelectrification were studied. The specimens were subjected to friction during one cycle lasting 60, 300, 600 and $1.2 \cdot 10^9$ s. The TSC spectra of the coatings manifested two typical peaks: the low temperature one in the range of 303 K and the high temperature one in the range 383–403 K, the high temperature peak tending to bifurcate as the friction extends.

A different pattern is observed when the number of cycles is varied together with the intervals between them. The increasing number of cycles reduces the high temperature peak, i.e. the electret charge as the variations of the ESCD evidence it under different friction conditions. As the interval is increased the ESCD grows noticeably. It can be explained by the fact that continuous and concurrent electrification processes produce the electret charge with consecutive appearance of the space charge domain (SCD), because the existing electron states in the SCD field are ionized, the emission phenomena occur and the charges are relaxed. Such relaxation primarily occurs in the interval between the cycles: the charges in the fast surface states are the first to reduce followed by those in the slow states. The charge relaxation becomes faster as the interval grows. Subsequent friction cycles cause the filling of the vacant high-energy traps and the ESCD goes up.

So, it can be concluded that such unsteady systems are capable to undergo self-organization when collective, cooperating.

CONCLUSION

Application of the basic postulates of the electrical theory of adhesion to the explanation of the regularities of electrification of polymers in friction and conclusions of the electron theory of disordered systems and surface states have allowed to verify the mechanism of electrification. The presence of surface states and their attraction of electrons injected from the metallic counterbody when the contact is broken produce an electrical charge on the surface of the polymer specimen. The triboelectrical field of the surface charge produces charge redistribution in the surface region producing the spatial charge region. A double electrical layer appears along the polymer – metal boundary. The charge density and the structure of the layer are governed by the characteristics of the surface states.

The mechanism of electretization of polymers in friction seems to be the following: during electrification a space charge and a spatial charge region appear causing polarization of a polymer material in the field and (with the account of injected charges) an electret state is generated. The parameters of the state are conditioned by the free injected charge carriers and polarization. The triboelectret state significantly affects the frictional characteristics of polymers.

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